

Methodological remarks for the achievement of reading comprehension in the university context

Observaciones metodológicas para el logro de la comprensión lectora en el contexto universitario

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Abstract

The development of the reading comprehension skill is one of the most important purposes in the Cuban National Education System. Reading favors the acquisition of linguistic habits and skills, and improves the linguistic communication process as a way of having command of the language. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to methodologically sustain the reading comprehension skill from a linguo-didactic approach in the English language program. Different theoretical methods such as analytical-synthetic and historical-logical were used, as well as document analysis during literature review. It is concluded that the reading comprehension skill may contribute to the formation of would-be foreign language teachers from the Foreign Languages Major, then it is essential to teach it from a linguo-didactic approach.

Keywords: reading comprehension, university context, and linguo-didactic approach

Resumen

El desarrollo de la habilidad comprensión lectora es un de los propósito más importantes en el Sistema Nacional de Educación. La comprensión lectora favorece a la adquisición de hábitos y habilidades lingüísticas y mejora el proceso de comunicación lingüística como una forma de tener dominio de la lengua. Por tanto, el proposito de este articulo es sustentar metodológicamente la habilidad comprensión lectora desde un enfoque linguo-didáctico en la carrera de Lenguas Extranjeras. Diferentes métodos teóricos tales como análisis-síntesis e histórico-lógico se emplearon, así como el análisis de documentos durante la revisión de la literatura. Se llega a la conclusión de que la habilidad comprensión lectora puede contribuir a la formación de los futuros profesores de lenguas extranjeras de la especialidad de lenguas extranjeras, entonces es esencial enseñarlo desde un enfoque linguo-didáctico.

Palabras clave: comprensión lectora, contexto universitario, enfoque linguo-didáctico

Introduction

Currently, the development of reading becomes a challenge for man due to the flow of information that is shared in social life. It is of great importance for life and for man's intellectual activity. Reading is a tool used as a source of entertainment and a means of enjoyment, as well as a communication tool to promote the comprehensive formation of many readers. Today, reading is regarded as a fundamental means of communication and knowledge. Besides, the majority of the information disseminated all over the world is done in written way; thus, reading is of great social, educative and practical importance and it is part of the verbal activity theory.

In addition, reading is a medium that favors the development of the human brain through the use of psycholinguistic mechanisms. When reading takes place, the eye muscles and the five senses of the human being are stimulated and it permits the acquisition of the printed codes. The teaching of reading begins to form part of the basic curriculum of foreign language courses and becomes an essential subject for the formation of habits and linguistic skills in students and teachers. Nowadays, this skill is an essential component dealt with in the Integrated English Practice discipline in the university context. It is of paramount importance for teaching a foreign language. It is evident that comprehension enables the development of psychological processes that can directly or indirectly affect the way of reading

and understanding of the language material.

The importance of reading in the life of human beings and in social practice is significant. Learning to read is to develop intellectual and cognitive abilities in any of the contexts that is carried out. However, in the course of teaching of reading, not only reading is used as an instrumental skill or an educational purpose, but also it is necessary to understand the ways in which the reading comprehension process must be developed for pleasure.

According to Vera (2016) reading is characterized by the following distinctive elements:

- Reading is a form of communication.
- Reading is an interactive process.
- Reading is an active process that develops cognitive skills.

In the same way, reading as a receptive skill function as a tool that provides knowledge about other sciences and develops from stages that are essential in the comprehensive development of the student in the university context.

The development of reading has as essential objectives to deepen the morphosyntactic knowledge from the generalization, interpretation and application; achieve the analysis and synthesis of lexical, grammatical and morphosyntactic structures as core elements to achieve a global understanding of the text; and also, to develop textual and reading competence through the use of dictionaries and reference sources in the English language.

Many authors such as Antich (1974), Antich (1986), Abbott & Wingard (1989), Cross (1992), Brown (1994), Acosta (1996), Ur (1996), Acosta (2009) and Garcia (2010), have investigated the problem within reading and the teaching of reading in general. The reading comprehension skill is a recognition and reproduction skill that provides values in the students and scholars, and at the same time, it develops language habits and ways of performance.

The development of reading requires the linguistic material to be analyzed in class. The way the students can improve their reading skills and habits. The way of developing reading strategies so that the students can deal with different kind of texts and in which way the students become in independent readers. The previous aspects show that reading contribute to the students' comprehensive formation and their character and behavior.

Several research studies have focused on reading and reading comprehension. Such is the case of Enriquez (1997) who proposes a methodological strategy for the treatment of the critic-valuating reading in the English Language; Castillo (2017) who elaborated a set of tasks to develop the inference subskill in the reading comprehension process in the English language with specific purposes in third academic year students majoring in tourism at the university of Havana.

On the other hand, Vera (2016), supports a comparative study of the syllabuses of the English subject in the development of the reading comprehension skill; Martínez (2013) designs an optional course of English reading with specific purposes aimed to students majoring in plastic arts at the Higher Institute of Arts, and Castillo (2009) sustains a strategic conception of the development of the reading comprehension, based on the holistic analysis of legal texts. Procedures for its implementation at the university of Pinar del Rio.

Many attempts have been made to describe the nature of reading, but it is not enough to improve the reading skill. Even so, the students majoring in foreign languages have met some difficulties, which hinder the acquisition of the reading comprehension skill. On one hand, they do not totally understand the linguistic material in terms of quantity of information, types of information and structure of information in the treatment of hypertexts in class. On the other hand, they do not recognize the linguistic means of reading (vocabulary, grammar forms and structures, pragmatic information and semantic structure of texts) taught in class.

Given that a detailed analysis of the various factors that intervene in the teaching of reading, shows the possibilities of the authors of the recent work to focus his attention on the elements that make reading comprehension possible from a linguo-didactic approach in the university context. Then, the purpose of this paper is to theoretically sustain the reading comprehension skill from a linguo-didactic approach in the English language program.

Development

The word *comprehend* comes from Latin 'comprehendere' and means understand, penetrate, reach, discern or decipher. A conceptualization of comprehension is offered below. According to Manuale (cited by Leyva, Turrubiarres & Colunga, 2021) comprehension is a state of training to exercise certain comprehension activities such as explanation, exemplification,

application, justification, comparison and contrast, contextualization and generalization. In addition, Duque and Vera (cited by Abad, Díaz & Olmos, 2022) define comprehension as the way of inferring and that inferring is building a model of the real or fictitious situation to which the text refers, beyond the text itself. Likewise, Lucas & Chancay (2022), express that comprehension is the process of elaborating meaning by learning the relevant ideas of the text and relating them to the ideas that one already has, it is the process through which the reader interacts with the text; in this sense, reading becomes a strategic tool since it deliberately acts and constantly monitors his own comprehension. For the authors, comprehension is a bilateral process through which the reader interacts with the text and appropriates certain information.

Reading comprehension is a process that intervenes in the development of human language. It has been defined by an important group of researchers and linguists taking into consideration the communicative, interactive, social, cultural and linguistic aspects. Therefore, comprehension implies the understanding of all the printed codes of the text. First, Grellet (1981) understands reading comprehension as a written text in order to extract the required information from it as efficiently as possible. Secondly, Dijk and Kintsch (1983) support comprehension as an integral and highly complex process that implies the construction of a mental representation that accounts for the global meaning of the text. For Anderson and Pearson (1984) consider that comprehension as it is currently conceived, is a process through which the reader conveys a meaning in his/ her interaction with the text.

However, Enríquez (1997) states that reading comprehension is an active, productive, interactive and creative process where the reader, in an internal dialogue with the author through the text, constructs and/or reconstructs the meaning according to his reading purpose. In the Teaching Knowledge Test course for teachers taught by Spratt, Pulverness, & Williams (2011), reading is a receptive skill that has to do with the reader's reaction to the text read. On the other hand, Ababa (2016) considers that reading comprehension refers to the fact that the student actively reads to construct meaning from the text and understands it. On the other hand, Uña (2021) expresses that reading comprehension is understood as the result of the interaction of two capacities: the recognition of written words and the comprehension of

the oral language. Finally, Contreras (2021) refers that reading comprehension is the ability of the human being to understand the meaning of what he reads in all its dimensions.

A detailed analysis of the definitions expressed above, allows the authors to determine trend features such as:

- Extract the required information.
- Comprehensive and highly complex process.
- Construct meaning through interaction with the text.
- Active, productive, interactive and creative process.
- Production of meaning from the text.

Taking the aforementioned elements as a starting point, and based on the knowledge of the authors, reading comprehension is assumed in this research as the complex, active and simultaneous process that occurs through the typical interaction of the reader, text and context in order to achieve the construction of meanings conveyed in written way.

Reading comprehension is based on the linguo-didactic approach, which is regarded as the systemic premise, which determines the way of establishing, on the basis of linguistic and didactic dimensions, the components and structures of language and emphasizing on the integration of knowledge, habits, skills, and psychopedagogical capacities to make sure the well-organized learning of the object language.

Linguistically speaking, reading is a communicative skill that involves language factors such as: vocabulary (selection of the appropriate words in a certain context), grammar (the correct use of grammar forms and structures), pronunciation (provides the correct articulation of the printed codes); besides, it comprises the phonological, morphological, lexical and syntactical rules, as well as sociocultural aspects. In addition, reading comprehension is part of the verbal activity theory. On the other hand, the comprehension process is one of the psycholinguistic mechanisms of the English Language.

Reading comprehension is based on Vigotsky's theory (1979) from the historical-cultural approach. This theory suggests that social interaction leads to continuous changes in thought and behavior that can vary greatly from culture to culture. Basically, this theory focuses

on the development as a fundamental category that depends on the interaction between people and tools provided by culture to form their own conception of the world. This is how reading comprehension proceeds, characterized by the dynamics of its activity in a social environment, in active interaction with readers and the text. Similarly, Vigotsky (cited by Rico, 2003) refers to the zone of proximal development as the distance between the actual level of development determined by the ability to solve a problem and the level of potential development, determined through problem solving under the guidance of an adult or in collaboration with another more adult partner. In the case of reading comprehension, something similar happens, levels of help are offered to our students with the collaboration of other students and the supporting materials (oral, written or audiovisual), through a set of tasks that favors the student gradually interprets, understands and extrapolates the different types of information expressed in the text.

According to García (2007), there are different types of comprehension in line with the purpose of the author and the type of reading:

- Literal comprehension is the purpose of reading to understand, or remember the information explicitly contained in the passage.
- Inferential comprehension aims to read for information that is not explicitly supported in the passage using the author's experience, intuition, and inference.
- Critical comprehension is the process by which one reads in order to compare information in a passage with the reader's own knowledge and values.
- Appreciative comprehension, according to Richards (cited by Garcia, 2007), has the purpose of reading to obtain an emotional response or another type of valued response from a passage.

However, the organization, structuring and implementing of the reading components make up the didactic conception of the reading comprehension skill, that is to say; the conception of reading comprehension skill in terms of principles, approaches, mechanisms, subskills, levels of comprehension, types of reading and the learning cycle of the reading comprehension skill in the English Language.

Reading comprehension skill is governed by some principles proposed by Grellet (1981) and Williams (1986) for its development in the classroom:

- Take the paragraph or the text (not the sentence) as the unit of work.
- Use authentic texts, as far as possible.
- The text should be interesting for the learner and, if possible, also for the teacher, since this increases motivation.
- Starting from the global understanding and moving towards the details, which helps to develop the comprehension of the organization of the text as well as the ability to anticipate, infer, etc.
- The class work should be a reflection of the nature of real reading: with a determined and interactive purpose, that is, reconstructing the author's message.
- In the reading session, the fundamental activity should be reading certain texts, not listening to the teacher, or talking about the text. Activities must be flexible and varied; variety encourages motivation.
- Intensive reading must be combined with extensive reading, adapted to the level of the learner.
- The role of the teacher is not so much to explain the text and give information, as to organize and advise.
- Explaining the students the meaning of a text is not the same as developing their reading comprehension; for this, it is necessary to help the students develop cognitive strategies that allow them to reconstruct the author's original message, interpret it and value it. For example, before reading an invoice, a competent reader identifies the type of text and activates some knowledge schemes related to the organization and information that characterizes the text in question.
- Integrate reading comprehension with other skills.
- It should be clear that there are some reading approaches at your disposal for tailoring classes for particular contexts:

1. Holistic or synthetic approach.

This approach is known in English as the top-down approach. The term holistic has to do with the organic or functional relationship between the parts and the whole (Webster's dictionary: 397). The synthetic term focuses on the understanding of the global, emphasizing the specific elements of the reading activity or process. Some linguists consider it as the mental model that goes from the general to the specific. Other authors such as Aguiano (2012) refers to this as a descending approach because the reader starts from the global recognition of phrases, words and then their elements such as syllables, phonemes and letters are analyzed, that is, in a descending manner. Also, Smith; Torres (quoted by Gago, 2021) consider it a descending model because it is part of the strategies that the reader uses to give a global meaning to the text, through the analysis of its components and the combination of what has been read with previous knowledge. On the other hand, the reader creates a hypothesis about what he is going to read and as he progresses in reading, he generates the verification of his anticipations. Also, the reader uses semantic and syntactic knowledge and emphasizes on coherence and cohesion.

Therefore, this approach focuses on the reader and starts from the general to the specific, that is to say, it begins with the recognition of higher units to the specific elements of reading (printed codes). In this approach, the global understanding of the contents of linguistic materials is evidenced by analyzing from the most general levels of the language to the most specific ones: from the text, to sentences and phrases, to the word, to the morpheme, and, finally, to the phoneme.

Reading comprehension in its more detailed analysis based on the use of this approach takes as its starting point the knowledge of these units and the combination of them to later interpret the meaning of each one of them and obtain the required information or the message of the writer or author. This approach not only considers the text or its decoding, but also takes into account the reader's previous experiences to build anticipations of their own content and verifies them as they are read. Finally, in this approach the mental processes that the reader must promote to understand a text of any kind are manifested: observation, analysis, synthesis, generalization, induction, deduction, etc.

2. Analytical or atomistic approach.

This approach is known in English as the “bottom-up approach” and tends to place the linguistic analysis of the text at the center of reading comprehension. The term atomistic emphasizes the process composed of simple elements. According to Webster's dictionary, the term analytic is used to refer to the separation of something into integral parts or constituent elements. (p.56) Aguiano (2012) refers to this as ascending because the elements that make up a text are processed firstly; that is, it begins with the letters, then the words, in an ascending and sequential manner, until the more complex units such as phrases are understood., sentences, which lead to the understanding of the text. On the other hand, Gough (cited by Gago, 2021), is the ascending model, which is based on processes where one ascends from the recognition of letters, which make up syllables and then words; until reaching the understanding of the sentences expressed in the text.

The atomistic approach focuses on the text and its purpose is the linguistic and segmented analysis of the text from its simplest elements to its most complex ones. It ponders the reader's transit from the lower levels of the language to the more complex ones. This conception is based on the exegesis of this approach taking into account the phonological, morphological, lexical, syntactic and textual level (understanding of ideas or paragraphs, fragments, and so on). From this perspective, several techniques are used to favor the development of reading comprehension. The analysis of the text starts from the sound - spelling relationship and emphasizes the meaning; then, it makes necessary the use of phonological techniques such as substitution, rhyme, combination or mixture and the sequence that make possible the understanding of unknown words by the readers. The use of each of them helps to interpret the meaning of the linguistic codes expressed in the text, obtain the required information and achieve a global understanding of the text in a coherent and efficient way.

3. Interactive approach.

The approach (or interactive model) has its foundations in authors such as Anderson & Pearson (1984); Smith (1978); Spiro, Bruce, Brewer (quoted by Cooper, 1990) suggest a new interactive model, and in turn, state that comprehension is the result of the interactivity of two types of information: the reader's prior knowledge and the ideas that it provides. That is, the rise from lower levels to higher levels where the information is propagated to higher

levels, and the information that is processed at each level functions as input. In another sense, verification occurs in elements of the levels (syntactic, lexical, graphophonic) through a descending process. Furthermore, the simultaneous interaction of knowledge of the world and knowledge of the text are used to construct the interpretation of the text (Aguiano, 2012, p. 18-19).

Likewise, authors such as Smith (1983); Carril and Deviel (1988), express that it comes, as its name indicates, from the interaction of what the reader already knows and masters, with the new reading to be carried out and the contributions that it can provide.

This approach is centered on the reader, who must manage decoding tools but also presupposes a previous motivation related to the fulfillment of achievements that are intended to be obtained after reading. The cultural and the linguistic are also important in this frame of reference (Gago, 2021:25-26). This approach assumes reading as a social and interactive activity because the reader constructs meanings by interpreting the printed codes expressed in written texts. In addition, it focuses its attention on the interaction between the reader, text and the social context. Bernhardt (quoted by Celce Murcia, 2000). The same author considers that reading is a sociocultural activity.

This approach is based on the integration of auditory, visual and linguistic mechanisms to achieve the appropriation of the meanings of the printed signs through the context. The absence of some of these elements implies the neglect of students' reading difficulties. Linguistic mechanisms compensate the interpretation of the word in segments and sequences of sounds that comprise these words, memory training through the acquisition of new words, proper articulation of these words, recognition of these in written form and the use of them in a certain context. However, auditory mechanisms make it possible to recognize words, groups and patterns of words orally and in sequence, as well as the combination of them for visual stimulation. Within these words, its forms can be found.

Instead, the visual mechanisms contribute to the recognition of visual letter cues, identification of word patterns, shapes, and left-to-right eye movement by progressing the senses in a succession of jerks. This approach focuses on the interaction of the reader and the text, and whose purpose lies in the integration of the elements of the previous approaches so that

the linguistic and segmented analysis of the text from the simple to the complex can be obtained as a final result and vice versa. Finally, it can be deduced that the construction of the meaning of a text starts from the author's previous knowledge about its content and the reader's experience.

Reading method:

The reading method arises from the need for scientific development in the feudal regime in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. At that time, reading became the most important and most possible tool for the bourgeoisie. Previously, reading was conceived as the essential objective in language courses. The reading method focuses its attention on the interpretation of codes for the comprehension of the information in the text. This method of reading emphasizes translation, obviates grammar and composition; and ignores the value of oral activity as a basis for reading. At present, this method has evolved in various directions and fields of the language, favoring the student in learning a foreign language by deepening the knowledge of linguistic elements and provides sociocultural and educational elements to the English foreign language learning process.

Reading skills:

According to Acosta (2005), the reading comprehension skill is operationalized from the sub-skills that compose it:

- Automatically recognize the written word.
- Identify the nature of the text in order to predict the form and content.
- Dialogue internally with the text.
- Search for specific information by speed reading.
- Specify the intention; know well what it reads for.
- Recognize the themes;
- Find out what the text is about.
- Classify ideas in main and secondary.
- Locate in the text the topic sentence and the generalizing sentence.
- Identify the main idea of a sentence, paragraph or text.

- Know what the author says about a topic.
- Identify relationships between text elements; identify relationship patterns, relationships between ideas; that is, the general structure of the text.
- Identify words that establish relationship patterns; be able to see the connections between ideas by using words such as: first, then, finally.
- Understand non-explicit information in the text.
- Recognize pronouns, referents and lexical equivalents as keys to cohesion.
- Infer from the context the meaning of new words.
- Look for the general idea of the text by means of a "quick look".
- Paraphrase; reproduce the text in the reader's words.
- Summarize, shorten the text including only the main ideas.
- Follow the clues in the text.
- Draw conclusions.
- Infer through the use of evidence.
- Understand the communicative value (function) of expressions.
- Visualize what it reads through drawings and diagrams (semantic maps).
- Read critically.
- Read quickly.
- Adjust the speed of reading according to the material and the objective.

Reading comprehension levels:

According to García, Arévalo & Hernández (2018), reading comprehension is measured through three levels of comprehension: textual level, which refers to the ability to identify information. The second level, called inferential, measures the ability to establish relationships between ideas, and the contextual level related to the assessment and validation of information from the context. On the other hand, Elosúa & García (cited by Arreola & Coronado, 2021) admit that in order to achieve a comprehensive reading, the levels that go from decoding, literal extraction, inferential comprehension, to metacomprehension.

However, in this work the following levels are assumed taking into account the teaching

contexts, students' diagnosis and the purposes of textual comprehension:

1. Interpretation is the primary level where the reader begins to move through the text under study. This is where we proceed to identify and determine information from the text; the characteristics of the texts, objectives, tasks, actions and operations. This level responds to what the reader thinks about the reading.
2. Comprehension is the intermediate level that allows you to develop tasks with a high level of complexity. This level responds to what is read. At this level, we proceed to develop the ability to establish relationships between the ideas expressed in terms of the inference of meanings and the global and specific understanding of the text; organization of ideas; determination of secondary and primary ideas and answers to information questions, etc.
3. Extrapolation is the last level of reading that seeks strategies and actions to answer how the thematic content of the text is applied to reality based on summaries, evaluation of information, opinions and conclusions. It is the level where students make comparisons between situations and processes, etc.

Types of reading:

Reading is a process that favors the cognitive and sociocultural development of the students. This receptive ability implies the comprehension of the information contained in the text through different types of readings. According to Folónkina (cited by Gonzalez, 2001), reading is classified taking into account the organization of work with the text: analytical, synthetic reading, with translation, without translation. According to the type of work with the linguistic material: intensive, comparative, without preparedness. However, the different types of reading do not show the procedural nature of the reading. Consequently, the same author addresses silent reading and classifies it as global reading, understood as the ability to quickly read a reading material to obtain general information about its content. On the other hand, the recognition reading refers to broad strokes that is raised about a certain problem without going into details of the information. Study reading, for its part, includes all the informative content of the text. This type of reading is slower and enables the students to develop the linguistic analysis of the text without any difficulty in comprehending it. This

reading focuses its attention on the comprehension, interpretation and fixation of the content of the text in the reading process.

Due to the importance that textual comprehension requires in English, the following types of reading are assumed: global reading (reading over), reading that seeks the general idea or the general comprehension of the text. In this type of reading, the linguistic material is totally or partially unknown. The first and last paragraphs, heading, abstracts, titles, subheadings and illustrations are included here. The reading of specific information search, is the type of reading that the subject is known, in general. This reading is the opposite of general information reading and its purpose is to extract specific information from the text, this involves searching for key words and ideas in the text. Intensive reading focuses your attention on seeking detailed information. This careful reading requires a high degree of comprehension and retention for a long period of time to short texts with a complete and detailed understanding. In addition, it develops a detailed analysis of vocabulary, important words and phrases, as well as grammatical elements aimed at studying in the language. Extensive reading is done for pleasure. It involves reading widely and in quantity. Extensive reading has as main purpose the general understanding of the text by extracting general meanings, so the reader not only focuses on the forms of the language, but on the content of the linguistic material. This reading is done with long texts containing deep contents.

The teaching of reading starts from the stages that make up the process of reading comprehension. To Solé (cited by Aguilar & Martínez, 2021) reading comprises subprocesses, understood as stages of the reading process: a first moment, of mental and affective preparation and clarification of purposes; secondly, the activity that includes comprehension elements of textual type, for the construction of meanings, and a third moment, its consolidation, making use of more complex cognitive mechanisms that allow synthesizing, generalizing, and restructuring concepts.

The learning cycle of reading is divided into three stages: before, while, and after reading. Reading instruction involves the acquisition of the informational content of the text by advancing the reader through the learning cycle in stages and teaching methods. The stage before reading is based on the preparation for reading. In this stage, the activation of

the knowledge and previous experience of the students is promoted in order to formulate hypotheses about the content of the reading.

This stage involves actions to:

- Motivation of the students towards reading material.
- Activation of prior knowledge of the subject, as well as the linguistic elements related to it.
- Anticipation of the form and content of the text.

In addition, in the development of this phase, the following elements are foreseen:

- Establish the purpose of reading.
- Make students aware of the type of text they deal with.
- Teach the essential vocabulary to understand the text.
- Become familiar with linguistic structures.
- Emphasize the structure of the text and the elements that characterize it.
- Use strategies that help to understand the linguistic content of the text.

The stage while reading is the moment in which the text is read silently or aloud. Here, activities are developed that favor the ability to interpret, understand and extrapolate the essential aspects of the text to achieve reading competence. During the reading process, in the phase during reading, the following is expected to be done:

- Focus students' attention on relevant information.
- Develop particular reading skills and strategies.

This stage involves the following elements:

- Monitor the text to be read.
- Infer the content of the text.
- Paraphrase the words of the text.
- Answer questions.
- Reread any of the misunderstood parts of the text.

- Summarize what has been learned from this part of the text.
- Determine the level of comprehension.

The stage after reading, is the moment in which a variety of activities are carried out that aim to deepen the level of comprehension of the students, through critical and creative reading.

The stage after reading refers to:

- Control the results of reading tasks.
- To know the reactions of the students towards the reading material.
- During the development of this stage, the following actions are applied:
- Answer questions to show understanding of the message of the text.
- Write about what has been read through guided questions.
- Talk about what has been read through debates, interviews, discussion, etc.

Conclusions

Reading comprehension plays an important role in learning a foreign language. Its application in the university context contributes to the acquisition of sociocultural and reading competence and the development of psychological processes in students and teachers. On the other hand, reading comprehension is based on the elements that favor the understanding of any linguistic material and its essential components (such as letters, words, phrases, sentences, etc.). The new trends that prevail in recent years in Cuban Higher Education aim at communicative language teaching and self-management of learning in foreign languages. Based on this premise, reading is supported in the linguo-didactic approach, which establishes the structures and components of language in relation to knowledge, skills, habits and capacities to be developed. Likewise, the theoretical and methodological aspects of the reading comprehension skill contribute to the development of the students' personality. At the same time, reading comprehension is developed by means of the use of the information encountered in different reliable sources of language. For this, the improvement of the reading comprehension skill in the university context favors to the over-all formation of the foreign languages teachers -to be.

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